

Organizing and augmenting cybersecurity knowledge using generative AI

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Abstract—With the rapid advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI), cybersecurity threats are becoming increasingly sophisticated. Static, human-curated approaches such as MITRE ATT&CK and CAPEC are often insufficient for companies to implement effective countermeasures, and security experts frequently face challenges in integrating these frameworks into their specific architectures. In this paper, we explore the application of generative AI to organize and enhance cybersecurity knowledge bases. We leverage multiple state-of-the-art Large Language Models (LLMs) to augment an initial dataset of attack-mitigation pairs, generating new countermeasures along with their prioritized execution order in a reasonable time frame. To evaluate the generated responses, we employ the LLM-as-a-Judge technique. Evaluations with Claude 3.5, DeepSeek R1, and human oversight show that top-performing models on general benchmarks also perform well in this specialized task, with more than 70% of responses rated 4 and 5 out of 5 for correctness, and the weaker models tend to perform the worst. Additionally, we discuss the challenges of running LLMs with a larger number of parameters on less powerful hardware, where the performance of such models can degrade significantly, even performing worse than their smaller counterparts. In such cases, advanced prompt engineering becomes necessary to improve results.

Our code and dataset are publicly available at “<https://github.com/martel-innovate/HORSE-GenAI-CKB>”

Index Terms—Generative AI, LLM, Security, Cybersecurity, MITRE ATT&CK, Knowledge Base

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era where cyber threats are growing in sophistication and frequency, understanding adversary behavior has become a cornerstone of modern cybersecurity. Defenders need structured frameworks to analyze, predict, and mitigate attacks effectively. Two primary approaches exist for organizing knowledge about adversary tactics and techniques: MITRE ATT&CK and CAPEC. MITRE ATT&CK [1] is a globally recognized knowledge base that catalogs adversary tactics and techniques observed in real-world cybersecurity threats. Widely adopted by both researchers and industry practitioners [2], it focuses on network defense and highlights the operational phases of an adversary’s lifecycle. On the

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other hand, CAPEC (Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification) [3] primarily addresses application security, detailing common adversarial techniques that exploit known vulnerabilities associated with CWE (Common Weakness Enumeration). A recent study by CLTC and McAfee [4] revealed that over 80% of enterprises utilize MITRE ATT&CK for threat protection, leveraging it to identify security gaps, implement policies, and conduct threat modeling. Despite its extensive adoption, the study also revealed that security professionals often face challenges in integrating the framework with their security tools. Mapping event-specific data to MITRE ATT&CK’s tactics and techniques can be complex, making it difficult to extract relevant information for specific use cases. Additionally, keeping security systems aligned with evolving frameworks like MITRE ATT&CK and CAPEC requires significant human intervention. Moreover, various cybersecurity knowledge bases exist, each tackling security threats from different perspectives, but linking them effectively remains a hurdle, particularly when explicit relationships between frameworks are not provided.

To address these challenges, we explore the application of generative AI, specifically large language models (LLMs), in enhancing cybersecurity knowledge organization and usability. The rapid advancements in LLMs have demonstrated remarkable adaptability and effectiveness across various domains, including cybersecurity [5]. These models, such as ChatGPT and Llama, trained on vast datasets, exhibit strong reasoning and decision-making capabilities, opening new opportunities for the cybersecurity community. LLMs offer an efficient way of integrating heterogeneous cybersecurity data sources into a unified, structured, and queryable database while maintaining the speed and reliability of traditional databases. In this study, we explore the potential of LLMs to develop a Common Knowledge Base component within the HORSE project [6] architecture. This component consolidates cybersecurity threats and countermeasures data from diverse sources, creating a dictionary of attacks and mitigations. Given the necessity of seamless integration with other components, maintaining a precise data format is of major importance. The primary challenge lies in aggregating a wide variety of security-related data from open sources and combining them in an automated, efficient, and trustworthy manner. To this end, we leverage state-of-the-art LLMs to extract, map, and enhance cybersecurity information.

The key contributions of this study are:

- 1) **Utilizing generative AI to build a structured cybersecurity database:** we employ LLMs to enhance CAPEC’s dataset, creating a more comprehensive collection of attack-mitigation pairs that are both machine-readable and human-readable.
- 2) **Developing a modular and extensible framework:** the implementation is structured in modular Python components, allowing flexibility in model selection, data extraction, and processing while enabling full automation with minimal human intervention.
- 3) **Evaluating performance through LLM-as-judge and Human-in-the-loop:** we generate cybersecurity knowledge using multiple LLMs, compare their outputs using two of the most advanced models available, and validate the results with oversight from cybersecurity experts.

II. RELATED WORK

Traditional knowledge bases have long been central to cybersecurity, exemplified by frameworks like MITRE ATT&CK [1], provide structured catalogs of adversary tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) derived from real-world observations. These manually curated frameworks deliver reliable threat intelligence, widely adopted for standardizing security practices. However, their static nature limits scalability and responsiveness to emerging threats, a challenge well-documented in prior studies, such as [7]. To address this, automation can enhance these traditional approaches, as evidenced by surveys on machine learning for network anomaly detection [8].

Efforts to overcome these limitations increasingly focus on aggregating heterogeneous data sources to enrich cybersecurity knowledge bases. Research integrating structured frameworks like CAPEC and CVE [3], [9] with unstructured data, such as social media or incident logs, demonstrate improved threat visibility [10]. Approaches such as the use of ontologies and data fusion [11] help in normalizing these diverse sources, though maintaining semantic consistency remains a challenge. This aggregation enables a comprehensive threat landscape analysis, essential for modern defenses, as evidenced by blockchain-based IoT security frameworks [12].

Taking this a step further, Generative AI (GenAI) is revolutionizing knowledge base construction by generating synthetic data. Research on Large Language Models (LLMs) fine-tuned for cybersecurity shows their ability to produce actionable content where manual efforts fall short [13]. This capability enables rapid adaptation to evolving threats, bridging gaps in traditional frameworks with automated, data-driven insights. Such scalability shines through in work using generative adversarial networks to craft realistic cyber threat intelligence reports, enhancing repository efficiency [14].

Beyond data generation, GenAI’s broader impact in cybersecurity includes automating threat analysis and defenses. Research shows LLM models like Llama and Falcon excel in classifying threats within unstructured data [15]. Despite risks of hallucination, GenAI reduces human workload and

boosts responsiveness, as noted in systematic reviews of LLMs in cybersecurity [5]. Complementary research on LLM benchmarks reinforces their rising influence on cyber defenses [16]. Building on these advancements, our work advances beyond prior research not only by leveraging LLMs to generate attack-mitigation data but also by integrating them into the comprehensive HORSE cybersecurity architecture.

III. HORSE ARCHITECTURE

A. General architecture

Fig. 1: HORSE Functional Architecture

HORSE (Holistic, Omnipresent, Resilient Services for future 6G wireless and computing Ecosystems) [6], [17] is a cutting-edge framework focused on end-to-end security in 6G networks. It leverages different AI-driven approaches, including LLMs, to tackle the vulnerabilities of 6G’s scalable and diverse environment. With a human-centric, and open-source design, HORSE delivers smart, cybersecurity measures for next-generation networks.

The HORSE architecture, shown in Fig. 1, integrates key functional units with a focus on threat intelligence and mitigation actions enforcement. After the network is monitored by the *Smart Monitoring (SM)* component, the *Data Collection*, the *Pre-processing*, the *Detector and Mitigation Engine (DEME)*, and the *Distributed Trustable AI Engine (DTE)* identify threats and notify the *Intent-Based Interface (IBI)* component. The IBI then interacts with the **Common Knowledge Base (CKB)**, an intelligent attack-mitigation database enriched with generative AI, to request suggestions on the mitigation action that should be enforced into the network that is under attack.

Subsequently, the *Reliability, Trust, and Resilience Provisioning (RTR)* module ensures these mitigation actions are translated into executable strategies, which are then carried out by the *End-to-End Proactive Secure Connectivity Manager (ePEM)* for deployment. The *Sandboxing (SAN)* and *Early Modeling (EM)* further support threat analysis and mitigation action enforcement by emulating the network, providing insights on the impact of various mitigation actions to the network’s functionality. The data privacy and security of the

Fig. 2: The Common Knowledge Base architecture

network, as well as the choices on the mitigation actions, are governed by the policies defined by the *Policies and Data Governance (PAG)* component.

B. Common Knowledge Base

Within the HORSE architecture, the Common Knowledge Base (CKB) (Fig. 2) functions as a centralized repository designed to store, manage, and enhance information related to network attack patterns and associated mitigation strategies. The CKB is a vital component in HORSE, powered by GenAI to stay ahead of evolving threats. Its modular design, implemented through an extensible Python framework, ensures independent and scalable functionality, facilitating maintenance, testing, and flexible deployment of its subcomponents.

The CKB serves as a centralized hub for data storage and management, maintaining an up-to-date repository of attacks and mitigation techniques. Through its REST APIs, it allows seamless integration with HORSE components while supporting queries for threat intelligence retrieval. The CKB leverages generative AI to synthesize and correlate data from external heterogeneous sources, autonomously update knowledge base entries, and generate mitigation strategies tailored to specific attack patterns. Additionally, it features threat prioritization and ranking, utilizing LLMs to assess risks, analyze patterns, and rank mitigation actions based on severity and potential impact.

To ensure robust data management and adaptive threat response, the CKB’s architecture integrates multiple components:

- **Centralized Database:** a structured storage system ensures secure, high-performance management of data regarding threats and mitigation techniques, optimized for rapid querying and scalability.
- **Dynamic Attack Resolver:** multiple Python modules that correlate various sources to identify newly documented attacks and mitigation actions, along with a data pre-processing pipeline to prepare them as input for the LLMs.
- **Mitigation Generator:** a Python module that uses generative AI to enhance the processed data, resulting in a comprehensive set of attacks and mitigations, along with the recommended order of execution for these mitigations.

- **API service:** a REST API-based interface facilitates seamless interoperability with HORSE components (e.g., IBI, EM), enabling efficient and secure data retrieval.

The CKB is implemented following a modular and extensible Python framework designed to enhance maintainability, scalability, and flexibility of cybersecurity data processing within the HORSE architecture.

Each core functionality is encapsulated within clearly defined, independent Python modules, allowing streamlined development, testing, and integration workflows. The **Dynamic attack resolver** handles the extraction of the cybersecurity knowledge from established external sources, such as CAPEC and MITRE ATT&CK. The *Search attack* module systematically parses attack patterns and the *Search mitigations* module searches for associated mitigation strategies. Then, the *Process data* module structures the extracted data and exports it into CSV files. These datasets serve as foundational inputs for the next module. The **Mitigation Generator** utilizes these structured datasets to dynamically generate prompts for generative AI models, ensuring standardized inputs and improving response consistency, also with a correct use of prompt engineering techniques. After preparing the prompt, the Mitigation Generator interacts with LLMs, such as Anthropic’s Claude or Meta’s Llama, through a dedicated API-handling module. It submits the prepared prompts to a running Ollama server, if the model is run locally; otherwise, it uses external APIs. Therefore, the Mitigation Generator manages the prompt submission and response retrieval process. Upon receiving responses from those LLMs, another Python module systematically stores these outputs into the **Centralized Database**. Once the database is populated, the **API Service** provides REST APIs that allow external components, such as HORSE components, to access the enhanced data stored in the database.

Finally, complementing the mitigation generation process, an evaluation-specific module follows a parallel workflow to assess the generated outputs. This module creates evaluation prompts fed to more sophisticated LLMs, with the generated mitigations as inputs. The output of this evaluation process comprises quantitative ratings accompanied by detailed qualitative explanations, facilitating an additional validation by cybersecurity experts through a human-in-the-loop review process.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Preparation Phase

1) *Dataset Selection:* The choice of the initial dataset is crucial, as it provides a solid foundation for the generative AI model, ensuring it builds upon a well-established and widely accepted knowledge base. Given the nature of our experiment and the desired structure of our final database, we selected a subset of attacks from the CAPEC framework, specifically from its hierarchical attack classification. CAPEC categorizes attack patterns into multiple levels, and we focused on the most granular level. From this, we extracted 100 distinct attack

patterns and copied them into a CSV file. Additionally, when available in the corresponding CAPEC entries, we included the associated mitigations for each attack.

2) *Model Selection*: We conducted an extensive evaluation of the available large language models and selected a subset based on the following criteria:

- **Accessibility**: Whether the model provides open weights and can be run on our machines or is only accessible through paid APIs.
- **Performance on Standard Benchmarks**: We prioritized models that performed well on widely recognized benchmarks, with a particular focus on the MMLU benchmark, which assesses a model’s ability to demonstrate extensive knowledge and problem-solving capabilities.
- **Suitability for Cybersecurity Applications**: We considered models specifically tested on cybersecurity benchmarks, such as SecEval [18] and CyberMetric-X [15], to ensure their effectiveness in security-related tasks.

Based on these criteria, we selected the following LLMs:

- Claude 3.5 Sonnet
- DeepSeek R1 8B
- Llama 3.1 8B
- Llama 2 13B
- Llama 2 7B
- IBM Granite 3 Dense 8B
- ALIENTELLIGENCE-cyberaisecurity

B. LLM-Based Mitigation Generation

Our experiments were conducted on a machine equipped with an **11th Gen Intel Core i5-1135G7 @ 2.40GHz** processor and **16GB** of RAM. The system runs Windows 11 Pro, and all models were executed using **Ollama** version 0.4.3 and **Python 3.12.2**, with the exception of Claude that can only be executed using Anthropic’s APIs. The experiments were performed in a controlled environment, ensuring consistency across all runs.

The MitigationGenerator was executed iteratively over all 100 attacks from the initial dataset, processing each attack on all selected models. During each iteration, the script selects a specific attack from the CAPEC dataset and utilizes the Ollama APIs (or other external APIs, such as Claude’s) to generate a comprehensive list of mitigations for the selected attack. In order to enhance the quality and relevance of the mitigation suggestions, any existing mitigations provided by CAPEC for the given attack are incorporated into the model’s prompt. This integration ensures that the model has a more complete context when generating responses.

In addition to producing the mitigation list, the models also assign a priority order to each mitigation, indicating its relative importance. Mitigations with a priority of 1 are considered the most critical and should be applied first to maximize security effectiveness. Furthermore, to ensure structured and automated processing, the prompt explicitly instructs the model to generate responses strictly in a predefined JSON format, without any additional text. This requirement allows the output to be directly parsed and analyzed by a Python script

without requiring human intervention. As we will observe in the results section, adherence to this constraint was crucial for the automation pipeline. Some models strictly followed this formatting requirement, while others deviated from it, and this compliance factor was taken into account during the evaluation of the generated responses.

Each time the model responds with a set of mitigations, the results are saved in a CSV file for further analysis. This data includes the initial attack and its corresponding mitigations extracted from CAPEC, the model used for inference, the inference time for each response, and the response. The collection of these metrics is essential for evaluating both the performance and accuracy of the model.

To safeguard privacy, all models were downloaded using the Ollama service and were executed locally on the system whenever possible. This approach ensures that sensitive data does not leave the local environment, thereby minimizing the risk of unauthorized data access or exposure during the process.

C. Evaluation Methodology

The generated results were evaluated based on two key factors: **model performance** (measured by inference time) and **response accuracy**. While performance evaluation was conducted using standard Python-based statistical analysis, as presented in the Results section, assessing accuracy required a more sophisticated methodology.

Given the large volume of data to evaluate, that is, one response for each of the 100 attacks across all the models used, we adopted the **LLM-as-a-Judge** methodology, as proposed by Zheng et al [19]. This approach was chosen due to its scalability and explainability, and the mentioned research has shown that under certain conditions, LLM-as-a-Judge achieves human-level agreement in evaluation of LLMs’ generated content.

For this evaluation, we selected **Claude 3.5 Sonnet** and **DeepSeek R1** as our judges, two of the most powerful models available at the moment, comparable in performance to GPT-4, which was used in the original LLM-as-a-Judge study. Similarly to the Mitigation Generation phase, we used Anthropic’s API to run Claude 3.5 Sonnet, while DeepSeek R1 was executed locally using Ollama.

To ensure a consistent and objective evaluation, we employed a **Role-Play Prompting** technique combined with the original prompt from Zheng et al.’s study. The final evaluation prompt used was:

”You are an expert in cybersecurity. Please act as an impartial judge and evaluate the quality of the response provided by an AI assistant to the user question displayed below. Your evaluation should consider factors such as format and correctness of the content. Begin your evaluation by providing a short explanation. Be as objective as possible. After providing your explanation, please rate the response on a scale of 1 to 5 by strictly following this format: ‘[[rating]]’, for example: ‘Rating: [[5]]’. User question: {initial_prompt}. AI assistant response: {response}.”

Both the *initial_prompt* and the AI-generated *response* were passed to the evaluator as dynamic variables to ensure a context-aware assessment of accuracy. We adopted a 1 to 5 rating scale based on:

- **Content correctness:** ensuring the response provided accurate and relevant mitigations.
- **Format correctness:** verifying whether the model followed the JSON format specified in the prompt, which is crucial for automating the attack-mitigation database enhancement process.

To facilitate both human oversight and automated statistical analysis, the evaluation prompt asked to produce a structured output that included a detailed, human-readable explanation of the assessment, followed by a final numerical rating, strictly formatted (e.g., 'Rating: [[5]]'), to allow automatic parsing by a Python script and statistical analysis, as presented in the Results section.

V. RESULTS

In this section, we present the results of our experiment.

Fig. 3: This bar plot illustrates the time in minutes required for each model to generate a response for each attack. The inference times are categorized by model and aggregated using minimum, maximum, and average values.

For **performance evaluation** at inference time (Fig. 3), the slowest locally run model was DeepSeek R1, with an average inference time of 3 minutes and 22 seconds, while the fastest was IBM Granite, averaging 1 minute and 18 seconds. It is evident that using Claude’s external APIs offers a significant advantage, as the model runs on high-performance remote machines instead of a local laptop with no Nvidia GPUs. Claude responded in an average of 10 seconds, with a minimum of just 2 seconds. These results highlight that, regardless of the task’s complexity, running an LLM is computationally expensive, and having hardware capable of handling this computational load significantly reduces inference time, especially when multiple runs are required. The graph also shows that all models in the Llama family, which have a similar number of parameters, performed the same, with response times ranging from 1 to 2 minutes on average. However, Llama 2 with

13B, which has more parameters than the other Llama models tested, was the slowest among them.

Fig. 4: This plot displays the aggregated evaluation ratings assigned by Claude 3.5 to all models, including itself. The best-performing models are those that also achieve higher scores in general-purpose benchmarks.

Fig. 5: This plot displays the aggregated evaluation ratings assigned by DeepSeek R1 to all models, including itself. While generally aligning with Claude’s evaluations, it occasionally hallucinates, likely due to hardware limitations.

To evaluate **response accuracy**, we used Claude 3.5 and DeepSeek R1 as judges. The results are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Both models agree that the **best performing LLMs** in generating accurate responses in the requested format are those that also perform well in standard benchmarks. These include **Claude 3.5, DeepSeek R1, IBM Granite 3, and Llama 3.1**, with more than 70% of responses receiving a score between 4 and 5 out of 5 from both judges. This evaluation aligns with expectations, as the responses from these models were found to be correct (providing appropriate mitigation actions), accurate, and structured exactly in the required JSON format. Among the **worst performing models**, an unexpected finding is that **Llama 2 13B** produced responses with lower quality compared to the similar but smaller **Llama 2 7B**. Specifically, 50% of Llama 2 13B’s responses were rated by Claude 3.5

Judge 2 out of 5, while Llama 2 7B had nearly 100% of responses rated above 2, with almost 40% receiving a perfect score of 5 out of 5. This suggests that either Llama 2 13B requires more refined prompt engineering to perform well or that the insufficient hardware resources negatively impacted its performance, making the larger model less effective than its smaller version. Although DeepSeek R1 Judge tends to be more generous with ratings, it also shows a preference for Llama 2 7B, with over 60% of responses rated 5 out of 5, compared to approximately 50% for Llama 2 13B. Another interesting observation is that, while Claude 3.5 followed the evaluation task precisely, **DeepSeek R1 occasionally hallucinated**, providing a reasonable explanation but an unexpected or inconsistent final rating (e.g., missing scores or out-of-range ratings). Again, we attribute this behavior to hardware limitations, as DeepSeek was run locally, whereas Claude 3.5 took advantage from a more powerful remote infrastructure. Overall, we are satisfied to see that **AI judges produced aligned evaluations**, which were further validated by human oversight. This reinforces the idea that LLM-based evaluation is not only scalable and efficient but also a reliable approach for assessing LLM’s generated content.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Our study demonstrates that LLMs have significant potential in developing cybersecurity knowledge bases to be used for specific applications and integrated into predefined architectures, such as HORSE. In fact, LLMs offer a scalable and efficient alternative to traditional methods or human intervention while maintaining the reliability of the generated content.

In our experiment, we collected an initial, incomplete dataset of cyberattacks and mitigations based on the CAPEC open database. We selected seven LLMs to enhance this dataset by generating additional mitigations, filling in gaps left by CAPEC. The inference time varied significantly across models, influenced by whether they were run locally or on powerful remote machines, as well as by the model’s complexity and number of parameters. To evaluate the quality of the generated data, we employed an LLM-as-a-Judge approach using two of the most advanced models available: Claude 3.5 and DeepSeek R1. The evaluations from both judges were aligned, with higher ratings given to models that already perform well on general purpose benchmarks. Interestingly, Llama 2 13B underperformed compared to its smaller 7B counterpart, suggesting that prompt engineering or hardware constraints may have influenced the results.

Future work will explore the impact of prompt engineering on model performance and response accuracy, in particular to understand the unexpected results of the Llama 2 models. Additionally, we plan to extend the experiment by testing much more LLMs. We will also evaluate how different hardware setups affect inference time and output quality, comparing systems with more or less computational power and testing both GPU and non-GPU environments.

In conclusion, the rapid advancements in LLMs over the past few years open new possibilities for cybersecurity re-

search. While the use of generative AI in building cybersecurity knowledge bases is still in its early stages, our findings highlight its strong potential for enhancing future cybersecurity frameworks.

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